

عَرَائِسُ الْمَجَالِسِ فِي قِصَصِ الْأَنْبِيَاءِ 'Ara'is al-Majalis fi Qaṣas al-Anbiya'

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Arabian Religions, Text, Hadith, Universal Chronicle, Islamic Traditions, Fiqh

Stories of the Prophets called 'Ara'is al-Majalis is the oldest book dealing with the stories of the prophets. Written by the scholar and commentator Abu Ishaq al-Thalabi, who died in 427 AH (1036 AD). Abu al-Qasim al-Qushayri said: I saw Almighty God in the dream, he was talking to me and I was talking to him, suddenly the Lord, his praise be to Him, said: behold the righteous man is coming towards us, so I turned around and saw Ahmed al-Thalabi coming. Al-Thalabi's book is a group of assemblies that include a group of chapters. In each assembly, al-Thalabi tells the story of one of the prophets. The assembly is similar to the Jewish midrash grouping. What brings al-Thalabi's book closer to the Jewish midrash is that it seeks to clarify the lesson of every story, and that his book is very close to Jewish mythology that's why, for example, there was no conflict between the jinn and angels before the creation of Adam, as we find that with al-Kisa'i, al-Tabari, and al-Masoudi...

Date Range: 1036 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Nishapur (or Naysabur)

Region tags: Asia, Iran

Naysabur or Nisabur or Nishapur is a city in central Iran. Yaqut al-Hamawi says about it: It is a great city with great virtues, It was the mineral of virtuous man and the source of scholars.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: 2019, العبيدي، شاذليّة، العنف المقدس في عرائس المجالس للنيسابوري، تونس،
- Source 2: محقّد، آليات اشتغال المحكي في قصص الأنبياء : عرائس المجالس للتعلبي نموذجاً، أطروحة، جامعة الحسن الثاني، 2004.
- Source 3: wagtendonk kees, The stories of David in al-Thalabi's 'Qisas al-Anbiya', Edisud , Aix-en-Provence, 1978
- Source 1: ABU ISHAQ AHMAD IBN MUHAMMAD IBN IBRAHIM AL-THALABI, 'ARA'IS AL-MAJALIS FI QISAS AL-ANBIYA' OR "LIVES OF THE PROPHETS", TRANSLATED AND ANNOTATED BY WILLIAM M. BRINNER, Brill, 2002. (The introduction).
- Source 2: A. RIPPIN (2003). Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies, 66, pp 249-251 doi:10.1017/S0041977X03260158
- Source 3: Roberto Tottoli (Reviewer), 'Arā'is al-majālis fī qīṣas al-anbiyā' or "Lives of the Prophets" as Recounted by Abū Ishāq Aḥmad ibn Muḥammad ibn Ibrāhīm al-Thalabī ("Studies in Arabic Literature", 24) by William M. Brinner Series: Quaderni di Studi Arabi vol. 20-21. doi: 10.2307/25802972

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://ia800600.us.archive.org/14/items/AhmadIbnMuhammadThalabiAraisAlMajalisFiQisasAlAnbiyaLivesOfTheProphetsLivesOfTheProphets/AhmacArais%20Al-Majalis%20Fi%20Qisas%20Al-Anbiya%20Lives%20of%20the%20Prophets_%20Lives%20of%20the%20Prophets.pdf
- Source 1 Description: The text of at-Thalabi translated in english
- Source 2 URL: https://library.kfcris.com/cgi-bin/koha/opac-search.pl?q=%D8%B9%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%A6%D8%B3%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D8%AC%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3&offset=0&sort_by=pubdate_c
- Source 2 Description: The different editions of the book of th-Thalabi

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: https://library.kfcris.com/cgi-bin/koha/opac-search.pl?q=%D8%B9%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%A6%D8%B3%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D8%AC%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3&offset=0&sort_by=pubdate_c
- Source 1 Description: Liste des éditions du livre dans la bibliothèque du Roi Faysal
- Source 2 URL: <https://books.google.tn/books?id=JLtsDwAAQBAJ&pg=PT2&dq=%D8%B9%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%A6%D8%B3%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D8%AC%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3&h>
- Source 2 Description: Une édition moderne mais le texte n'a subi aucun changement

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

–with Ink

Notes: There are many manuscripts of the book in various Arabic libraries. This means that the book is widespread among students and teachers of religious studies.

Reference: المكتبة الإسرائيلية الوطنية. "عرائس المجالس في قصص الأنبياء". <https://www.nli.org.il>, n.d.. [https://www.nli.org.il/ar/manuscripts/NNL_ALEPH002788562/NLI#\\$FL154147668](https://www.nli.org.il/ar/manuscripts/NNL_ALEPH002788562/NLI#$FL154147668).

Reference: "مخطوطات تركية". <https://www.quranicthought.com>, October 10, 2021.

<https://www.quranicthought.com/ar/books/%D8%B9%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%A6%D8%B3-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D8%AC%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3-%D9%81%D9%8A-%D9%82%D8%B5%D8%B5-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A3%D9%86%D8%A8%D9%8A%D8%A7%D8%A1-880/>.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

–Specify: Papier de livre normal

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: When we compare some of the manuscripts of the book (in view of the general content), we do not see any differences between the copies. Which means that the book has not been affected by changes through time, and the changes that can be between versions are the generally accepted changes as we see that when investigating ancient books.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: I do not think so

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: The book is available in public libraries, university libraries, and some private libraries. In Tunisia, for example, we find it in libraries of Zeitouna mosques, in universities (Zeitouna, Manouba...), and in some private libraries such as Ibn Ashour or Al-Neifer library .

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: Cela varie d'une école religieuse à une autre. Cependant, la plupart des ces écoles considèrent ce qui y est dit comme « des isra'iliyyat » (c.a.d. des propos de juifs) ces propos sont vus avec suspicion et méfiance, mais elles emploient ce qui y est dit quand elles en ont besoin.

Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

- ↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?
– No
- ↳ Are the scriptures alterable?
– No
- ↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?
– Yes
- ↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?
– Yes
Notes: What we find in the ath-Tha'labi book (the narrative functions; the common features between the biblical figures and the prophets mentioned in the Koran; the interpretative method which is based on the verses of the Koran and the sayings of the prophet Mohammad...) we find it in at-Tabari, Mas'oudi, Ya'qubi, at-Toussi... These stories are interpreted by any "connoisseur" of the Holy Quran whether he is a man of religious science or a profane narrator.
- ↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?
– No
- ↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)
– Yes
Notes: Les différences entre les spécialistes dans ce domaine sont subtiles. Il y a des différences claires, par exemple, la différence entre l'histoire de la création selon al-Tha'labi et l'histoire de la création selon al-Kisa'i est une différence claire, ainsi que la différence que nous voyons dans les noms de leurs deux livres : un livre qui fait clairement référence au midrash juif, qui est le livre d'al-Thalabi, et le livre d'al-Kisa'i fait clairement référence au corpus des hadiths.
- ↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?
– No
- ↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?
– Yes
Notes: nous pouvons voir dans la culture arabo-musulmane que les traditions prophétiques (Qasas al-Anbiya'), comme un genre littéraire, ne sont pas très bien accueilli dans les cercles scientifiques officielles. Oui on trouve ces traditions dans les livres de l'exégèse coranique, ou dans les récits historiques mais elles sont acceptées par le pouvoir symbolique des savants et surtout des savants de la tradition (علماء الحديث)
- ↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?
– Yes
Notes: Ce sont généralement des savants de la tradition ou des narrateurs dans des cercles publiques
- ↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?
– Yes
Notes: Oui généralement ce sont des hommes âgés (sages)
- ↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?
– Yes
Notes: Ceci dépend des auditeurs
- ↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?
– Yes
Notes: Le travail de ath-Tha'labi se repose sur les traditions soit des traditions islamiques ou des traditions bibliques. La méthodologie du choix des traditions est l'objet d'une science nommée Ta'dil wa Tajrih (التعديل والتجريح). Elle a été élaborée dans les siècles IX et X, at-Tha'labi vivait dans le XI siècle
- ↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: Oui, car ce qui était considéré comme des isra'iliyyat est devenu, avec al-Thalabi, une partie du corpus des hadiths

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: Malgré que la réponse "oui" semble être contradictoire avec la précédente, il faut signaler que la langue arabe est considérée comme sacrée, mais elle subit aussi pour ceux qui croient à sa sacralité des changements externe liés à sa relation avec d'autres langues

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

– Other [specify]: Les savants notamment Shafi'i qui croient que la langue arabe a été créée par Dieu et que Isma'îl était le premier homme qui a parlé l'arabe

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: Je crois qu'on ne peut pas donner une estimation du nombre de personnes intéressées à ce texte, en général c'est un public religieux qui s'intéresse aux récits du Coran ou qui étudie la religion et les religions comparées

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Le livre parle des histoires des prophètes et la fonction principale des prophètes est d'appeler les gens à croire en un seul Dieu et de les informer de ce qui les attend dans l'au-delà.

- ↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for all adherents?
– Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for all adherents?
– Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing or missionary work part of the historical culture of the community referenced in the text?
– No
- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?
– Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?
– Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?
– Yes
- ↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
– No
Notes: Si ces récompenses sont d'ordre matériel la réponse est non
- ↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
– No
- ↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
– Yes
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
– No
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?
– No
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?
– No
- ↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
– No
- ↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: non mais il a été édité plusieurs fois

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Le livre de Tha'labi est un groupe de livres, tout comme l'Ancien Testament est un groupe de livres. Il est un livre sur les histoires des prophètes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Il appartient à la littérature des légendes prophétiques

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: Il comprend les récit coranique (et biblique) des légendes des prophètes.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Il faut signaler que les récits des prophètes (Qasas al-Anbiya' قصص الأنبياء) s'intéressent aux récits coraniques (d'ailleurs ces récits sont appelés aussi les récits coranique (قصص القرآن). Ces récits se concentrent en grande partie sur l'histoire d'Israël, l'histoire des tribus autre qu'Israël comme Thamoud (ثمود), 'Ad (عاد)..

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: Une autorité religieuse en premier lieu (les prophètes), et politique (Loqman لقمان; Alexandre دوالقرنين)

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

Notes: Le cycle est le cycle des prophètes (الأنبياء) et des messagés (الرسول)

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Other [specify]: Les prophètes et les messagers sont des élus, et non les lignées

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: يقول التعلبي: "وقال أبو القاسم الحكيم: إن الله تعالى جعل ابن آدم بين البأوى والبلى، فما دام الروح في جسد فهو في 22 ص 22
ath-Tha'labi said Abu al-Qasim al-Hakim said: "God placed the son of Adam between affliction and decay. As long as the soul dwells in the body; he is in affliction; when the soul leaves his body, he is in decay; and then (at last) happiness comes to him, so he is between affliction and decay." p 42-43.

Reference: Ibn Muhammad Thalabi, Ahmad. 'ARA'IS AL-MAJALIS FI QISAS AL-ANBIYA' OU "VIES DES PROPHÈTES", Translated by William M. Brinner. Vol. 1. Brill: Brill, 2002.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: L'esprit à du pouvoir sur le corps, il y a différent type d'esprit (nafs), et la destinée du corps est liée à son obéissance à l'un des ces esprit

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally negative

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: The concept of the spirit in this book is the same concept as the Sufis. There is the blameworthy spirit, the spirit that commands evil, and the contented spirit... These types of spirit have varying degrees of control over the body.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: Le contraste entre l'âme et le corps n'est pas un sujet de controverse parmi les musulmans, car ils conviennent que l'âme est différente du corps. Le débat était sur savoir si Dieu nous ressuscitera de la mort en esprit et en corps ou seulement en esprit, et si nous entrerons au ciel ou dans les enfers en corps et en esprit, ou seulement en esprit.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– I don't know

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: The distinction between soul (luminous heavenly) and body (dark, earthy) dominated the relationship between soul and body

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: جاء في عرائس المجالس (ص 8) : "وروى سامة بن كهيل عن أبي الزرقاء عن عبد الله قال: الجنة اليوم في السماء السابعة فإذا كان غد جعلها الله حيث يشاء والنار اليوم في الأرض السفلى فإذا كان غد جعلها الله حيث يشاء. وأما بعد فعز الأرض فكافيك به حديث فارون حيث خسف الله به الأرض وبيداه وبأمواله , ففي الخبر أنه يخسف به كل يوم مقدار قامة فلا يبلغ قعرها إلى يوم القيامة , وقال النبي عليه الصلاة والسلام: بينما رجل يتختر في برديه وينظر في يوم مقدار قامة فلا يبلغ قعرها إلى يوم القيامة , وعطفه وقد أعجبت نفسه فخسف الله به الأرض فهو يتجلجل فيها إلى يوم القيامة." translation by William Brinner (p 13) Salamah b. Kuhayl—Abu I-Zarqa', quoting 'Abdallah: "Today Paradise is in the seventh Heaven, whereas tomorrow God may place it wherever He wishes, and Hell today is in the lowest Earth, but tomorrow He may place it wherever He wishes. As for what is beyond the bottom of the Earth, satisfy yourself with the story of Korah when God caused the Earth to swallow him up with his house and possessions. In the accounts (it is said) that He causes him to sink down in it a man's height deeper each day, but he will not reach bottom until the Day of Resurrection. And the Prophet said: 'While a man may strut around proudly in his garments, admire himself, and be pleased with himself, God will cause the earth to swallow him up and he will sink into it until the Day of Resurrection.'"

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

Notes: On comprend l'au-delà et le "en dessous" symboliquement

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

–Specify: Le langage de l'au-delà est l'arabe

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

–Specify: Le langage est syriac

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: Le texte est un recueil des récits des prophètes il peut indiquer ce qui a été enterré avec Adam ou autre prophète mais généralement on ne trouve pas d'indication des choses qui doivent être enterrées avec le cadavre

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Pour certains prophètes, surtout Adam puisqu'il est le premier à être enterré officiellement (après l'avoir lavé et prié devant son corps avant de l'enterrer)

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Yes

Notes: oui pour le Prophète Ibrahim et sa famille (Tha'labi (Arabic edition) p. 90)

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: non

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: Il est décrit parfois en termes anthropomorphiques

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– Yes

Notes: Non pas une vraie manifestation ou émanation non mais plutôt un Kalif.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No
 - Notes: Sauf le lien du Créateur et crée
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: Omnipotent, Qui sait tout, tout puissant
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - Notes: Il sait le passé le présent et le future, le monde d'ici-bas et le monde de l'au-delà.
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes

- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: C'est le Dieu des religions monothéistes
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes
 - Notes: Symboliquement
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living
 - Yes
 - Notes: A travers les choses ou les animaux symboliquement Comme les corbeaux dans le cas de Caïn tuant Abel. Comme l'incident de Salomon avec les fourmis, et l'incident de Salomon avec le tapis volant...
 - ↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
 - No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

- Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - Notes: L'ange de la mort par exemple
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - No
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - No
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
 - ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices?
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Le texte de Tha'labi nous raconte beaucoup d'histoire où les anges et les démons se manifestent aux hommes et communiquent avec eux

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: Ils volent, ils se déplacent à une vitesse très grande...

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

Notes: Iblis (Satan) est le père, parfois c'est lui même la mère, d'autre le serpent est la mère

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

Notes: Leur pouvoir peut atteindre beaucoup de domaine

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

–Specify: Les anges aussi sont organiés hiérarchiquement mais sans modèle familial

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Harut et Marut (43-44 ar. ed.) + (86 ff Brinner ed.)

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Oui mais ils sont très bien cachés dans un puit

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Notes: Première fille d'Adam et Eve, elle s'appelle Anak. Et une fée dont le nom est Amalah, et elle est la femme de Caïn. Et une nymphe nommée Turkah, et elle est la femme d'Abel... (p 39 ar.ed.) (p 75 ff Brinner ed.)

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: Oui surtout pour les normes qui concernent le mariage et la famille en général. يقول التعلبي في سياق لقاء النبي يوسف مع ملك الموت: "فقال يا نبي الله ما جئتك إلا مسلماً فإن الله تعالى لا يمتك حتى يجمع بينك وبين يوسف ولو كان في الصخرة التي عليها قرار الأرضين وما أذن الله في زيارتك إلا لأشرك وأجيبك عما تسألني عنه وإن شئت أعلمتك لماذا ابتليت بفقد ولدك: قال له فأعلمني يا عزرائيل، فقال يا إسرائيل الله هل تذكرت الجارية التي اشتريتها عام كذا في شهر كذا ثم فرقت بينها وبين أبويها قال نعم يا ملك الموت كأنه كان بالأمس فقال له ملك الموت فلأجل ذلك ابتليت بفقد الولد؟ وهل تعلم لماذا ابتليت بفقد البصر قال لا قال: أمرت يوماً بذيح جذعة فذبحتها وشويتها في يوم كذا في شهر كذا فمر تميم العابد العبد الصالح بك وهو صائم ما أفطر منذ أسبوع فاشتمت قنار الشوى فلم تطعمه شيئاً فعند ذلك أعتق يعقوب من كان بحضرته من العبيد والإماء وأمر أن يذبح كل يوم من أغنامه كبشاً ويفرق لحمهما على الفقراء والمساكين فقبل الله ذلك منه وشكره عليه وأناه الفرح فعند ذلك قال يعقوب- يا Al-Thalabi says in the context of the story of Joseph and his meeting with the Angel of Death: "He said, "Prophet of God, I have come only to greet a Muslim. For God will not let you die until He rejoins you with Joseph, even if it had to be inside the rock on which the Earth rests. God permitted me to visit you only to bring you the good tidings and to answer what you will ask me. If you want, I shall tell you why you have been afflicted by the loss of your son." He said, "Do tell me, cAzracl." He said, "O you whom God called Israel! Do you remember the slave girl you bought in such-and-such a month in such-and-such a year, and separated her from her parents?"—"Yes, Angel of Death, I remember it as though it were yesterday."—"Because of this deed you were afflicted with the loss of your son. And do you know why you were afflicted with the loss of your eyesight?" "No," Jacob said. "A lamb was slaughtered and roasted on your orders," said the Angel of Death, "on such-and- such a day in such-and-such a month. When Tamim the pious, upright slave passed by, (after fasting for a week), he smelled the aroma of the roast, but you did not give him anything to eat." Thereupon Jacob set free the male and female slaves in his possession, and gave orders to slaughter each day two sheep of his flocks and to distribute their meat to the poor and the needy. God accepted this offering from him and thanked him for it and brought him deliverance, whereupon Jacob said, "Go, my sons, and inquire concerning Joseph and his brother..." p 224-225.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Notes: Certainement on voit cela dans le récit de Caïn et Abel (p 38-39 pour l'édition arabe et p 76 pour l'édition anglaise)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

- Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest
 - Yes
 - ↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].
 - No
 - ↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)
 - No
 - ↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?
 - No
 - ↳ Other sexual practices
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
 - Notes: Certainement mais avec cette remarque pertinente: Dieu n'intervient pas pour assurer le bon déroulement des rituels
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: Non

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - Yes
 - Notes: Ces êtres surnaturels ne font rien qui n'est pas ordonné ou commandé par le Dieu suprême
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done by other entities or through other means
 - Yes
 - No
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly
 - No
 - ↳ Other
 - Yes
 - Notes: Tout chatiment infligé par ces êtres revient au Dieu suprême
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group
 - Yes
 - No

- ↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?
 - No
- ↳ Other form of punishment
 - Specify: être privé de voir Dieu et d'être avec le prophète Mohammad
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of bad luck?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Political failure?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Defeat in battle?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Disaster on journeys?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other?
 - Specify: N'importe quel sensation de douleur physique, psychique ou sociale peut être une punition
- Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - Yes
 - Notes: Puisqu'il est l'omnipotentiel et tout revient à lui
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - Yes
 - Notes: Puisqu'il sont l'intermédiaires entre Dieu et l'Homme
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly
 - No
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
 - No
 - ↳ Other?
 - Yes
 - Notes: L'extrême récompense est de voir Dieu
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of good luck?
 - Yes

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: Toute sensation de bonheur est une récompense

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified

– No

↳ Coming in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ Coming on a specified date

– I don't know

Notes: La réponse est "on ne sait pas" c'est une date que Dieu seul la connaît

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future

– Yes

Notes: Le livre de Tha'labi ne précise pas si c'est proche ou non mais il appartient à une culture qui croit que le Messi ou le Mahdi va venir très prochainement.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

↳ Coming has already passed

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

↳ Other purpose

–Specify: La paix dans le monde

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ At specified time in future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Field doesn't know

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Field doesn't know

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

↳ Establishment of new political system

– Yes

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– Yes

↳ Other form of eschatology?

–Specify: La forme qu'on peut voir dans le texte est très proche de l'eschatologie juive

- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive
 - No
 - ↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive
 - Yes
 - ↳ All members of the sample region will survive
 - No
 - ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton
 - No
 - ↳ Other survival condition [specify]
 - Specify: Rien de spécial qu'on ne voit pas dans l'eschatologie juive

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: C'est par le biais de la narration qu'elles sont mentionnées. Dans le récit d'Adam nous trouvons les normes du mariage, et les normes de la vie commune (Cain et Abel). Ces normes sont pas présentées de la façon d'un discours de législation (Fiqh *فقه*)

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

- Strongly present & highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

- Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

- Yes

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

- Yes

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

- No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

- No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

- No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

- No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

- All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle)
– Yes
- ↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility

- No
 - ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
 - ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Yes
 - ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
 - ↳ Optimism/hope
 - Yes
 - ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - Yes
 - ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
 - ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - Yes
 - ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - No
 - ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - No
 - ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other important virtues
 - Yes
- Notes: Ascétisme; Dévotion à Dieu...

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: Oui comme le pèlerinage, la participation aux rituels d'enterrement des prophètes ou des rois, l'écoute aux communications (leçons, prêches) religieuses

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Notes: Aujourd'hui le nombre des pèlerins est estimé à des millions (4 million)

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

Notes: Le pèlerinage est un rituel annuel, la prière du vendredi (صلاة الجمعة) est hebdomadaire, les rituels de l'enterrement est occasionnel.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?
– Yes

↳ Comedy?
– Yes

↳ Tragedy?
– Yes

↳ Epic entertainment?
– Yes

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?
– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?
– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?
– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?
– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?
– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?
– No

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?
– No

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?
– I don't know

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
– No

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
– No

- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Les offrandes faites sont généralement les agneaux
- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - No
- ↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it required?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Le texte parle de beaucoup de lieux sacrés.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:
– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?
– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?
– Other
Notes: Non

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?
– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?
– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?
– No

Other forms of welfare?
– Yes
Notes: Parmi les valeurs qu'il prône la tolérance et la coopération

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?
– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Yes

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– I don't know

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

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